

EMPLOYEES’ MOTIVATIONAL TOOLS AND ORGANIZATIONAL PRODUCTIVITY IN FEDERAL ESTABLISHMENTS IN SOUTH-SOUTH NIGERIA

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<p>Keyword: Employees’, motivational tools, organizational productivity Federal Establishments.</p>	<p>Abstract: <i>This study examined employees’ motivational tools and organizational productivity of federal establishments in South-South Nigeria. The research adopted descriptive survey research design. The population for this study was twenty federal establishments with over 2000 staff across all State in South-South Nigeria and a sample size of two hundred and seventeen senior staff of federal establishments in South-South Nigeria. The study used questionnaire instrument, and data were analyzed in the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) Version 22. The hypotheses were tested using Simple bivariate regression analysis at a significance level of 0.05. The results of the findings showed that there is a positive significant relationship between promotion and organizational productivity of federal establishments in South-South Nigeria. It was also revealed that there was a strong positive significant relationship between employees’ allowances and organizational productivity of federal establishments in South-South Nigeria. Also, the study also revealed a strong positive significant relationship between flexible work arrangement and organizational productivity of federal establishments in South-South Nigeria. Furthermore, the study also revealed a strong positive significant relationship between conducive work environment and organizational productivity of federal establishments in South-South Nigeria. Therefore, the study concludes that motivational tools through conducive work environment, flexible work arrangement, employee’s allowance and promotion significantly influences organizational productivity by way of improved effectiveness and efficiency. The study recommends that Federal establishments should provide conducive work environment for employees in order to motivate them in yielding higher organizational productivity. Federal establishments should schedule their employee where they can give their best. Employees should be motivated through a good pay package to optimize productivity. Employees’ promotion further boost productivity better than financial rewards.</i></p>
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INTRODUCTION

The success of any organization as a matter of fact depends largely on the motivation of the employees. Human resources are essential to the prosperity, productivity and performance of any company. Motivation is the key to creating an enabling environment where optimal performance is possible. This leads to the question how then do we ensure that the individual motivation is at its peak within the organization or workplace (Chapman, 2004)? Every employee or worker has his or her own set of motivations and personal incentives that ginger him or her to work hard or not as the case may be. Some are motivated by recognition whilst others are motivated by cash incentives. Whatever, the form of employee motivation, the key to promoting that motivation as an employer, is understanding and incentives (Mc Coy, 2000).

Employees' incentive programmes go a long way towards ensuring employees feel appreciated cared for and deemed worthwhile. This can go a long way to help with employee motivation across the board. The greatest thing about motivation is that it is individualized as such programs are tailored to suit the needs and wants of employees. Motivation does not only encourage productive performance but also show employees how much the company cares. Perhaps the most vital impact of employee motivation is that of increased productivity or

performance. This according to literature on the subject is the central aim of adopting employee motivational programmes thus, if you can increase employee motivation, productivity inevitably will follow suit (Ryan, 2011). Employee motivation promotes workplace harmony and increased employee performance. It is the key to long term benefits for the company. Motivated employees means staff retention and company loyalty, which in the short run will give birth to growth and development of business (Jishi, 2009).

After employees are hired and trained, it is important to motivate them to get the desired efforts from them, to achieve organizational objectives. Employee Motivation is an integral part Human Resource Management and it plays a crucial role in the long-term growth of an organization. It can be used in directing employees' behavior and actions for a constructive vision or goal. Proper motivation turns an employee into a loyal asset and helps in maintaining the retention rate. The word motivation is derived from Latin word 'movere' which means 'to move'. Motivation is something 'a desire, a want, need or drive that moves or spurs an individual to act in a particular way to achieve a goal or objective. People must be motivated to achieve certain goal or ambitions in life whether it may personal or business but it is always related with drives means eager to get something by anyway. In addition, motivation

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must be co-related with the ambitions. People are only motivated after setting up certain goals. Except natural behavior, motivation should only be on the base of emotional feelings. Motivation may come and draw non understandable reactions.

Employee motivation is the commitment, the energy levels, and the creativity that the employees bring to their job. Even though employees' motivation doesn't directly influence organization's growth, it is like a necessary pre-condition because lack of motivation among the employees can have a detrimental effect on their performance. Well-motivated employees are an asset to the organization and they write the success of organization and therefore, every organization should accord utmost attention to employees' motivation. A well-motivated employee stays with the organization through its thick and thin. Motivation is essential for establishing an effective relationship between the employer and the employees.

The concept of productivity is one of the most fashionable and frequently used in the domain of management today. It is described as the optimal utilization of resources in the production of goods and rendering of services that meets predetermined objectives. Motivation is the set of forces that cause people to choose certain behaviors from among the many alternatives open to them. An employee's performance typically is influenced by motivation, ability, and the work environment.

Some deficiencies can be addressed by providing training or altering the environment, motivation problems are not easily addressed.

Statement of the Problem

Major problems on employee motivation become evident when employees of an organization start perceiving that there is a wide mismatch between their expectations and organizational commitments. At times, such perceived expectations of the employees resulting in a significant drop in their perception. Non-involvement of employees' in the decision-making process within the organization leads to job dissatisfaction which eventually would lead to low productivity among others that would adversely affect the fortunes of the federal establishments and eventually the gross domestic product of the nation at large. Several research has been carried out on employee motivational tools, but there is no existing research that has covered South-South Nigeria. None of the existing research has been carried in the federal establishments to determine the level of dissatisfaction and how it can be mitigated. This among other gaps like content gap and theoretical gap form the basis for this research.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study is to examine employee motivational tools and organizational productivity in federal agencies in South-South Nigeria. The following are the objectives that the study sought to achieve:

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1. To examine how promotion of employee enhances organizational productivity
2. To determine how employee allowances triggers employee to be productive in the organization
3. To find out how flexible work arrangement enhances employee productivity.
4. To identify how conducive work environment leads to employee productivity in an organization.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Theoretical Review

Critical search of literature on the subject matter brought to the fore that, several theories of motivation have been developed, and were particularly relevant for work settings. But the most interesting revelation was the mere fact that, each of these theories highlights one or more of the variables of motivation. However, it was also relevant to acknowledge that almost all these theories were propounded by American psychologist/scientist.

This brings to the light an obvious and inevitable question: Do these theories apply only in the context of American culture and society or they can be used everywhere? The answer the researcher believes will be easy for everybody to answer after a careful examination and comparative analysis of the models.

Psychologist typically grouped motivation theories into two categories namely; the content theories and process theories. The content theories Hitt (2009), argued addresses the issue

of what needs a person is trying to satisfy and what features of the work environment seem to satisfy those needs. Such theories he was of the opinion tries to explain motivation by identifying (a) internal factors, that is particular needs and (b) external factors, particular job and work situation and characteristics that are presumed to cause behavior. The process theories work motivation dealt with the way different variables combined to influence the amount of effort put forth by an employee.

Malik, Ghafoor & Naseer (2011), in contributing to this school of thought said it attempts to explain and describe how people start, sustain and direct behavior aimed at the satisfaction of needs or reduction of inner tension. The major variables in this model are incentives, drive, reinforcement and expectancy. A comparative analysis of the two blocks obviously indicated that, the content theories place much premium or emphasis on the nature of needs to be satisfied and what actually motivates whiles the process theory has its focus on the actual process of motivation. It was realized during study that, the staff of Guaranty Trust has a way of standing up to tension (unsatisfied needs) and to a larger extent assumes that, there is one best way to motivate each and every one of them to sustain and direct their behavior at work.

Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs

This theory was propounded by Abraham Maslow. It was based on the assumption that employees are motivated by series of five

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universal needs, these range of needs he claimed the individual will be motivated to fulfill whichever is most powerful at the time of need (Maslow,1970). This need, literature makes us to understand he grouped them into; Lower order needs- which he claimed are dominant until they are at least partially satisfied. From this angle it can be realized that any normal human being would turn his attention to satisfy needs at the next level giving rise to higher-order needs which gradually becomes dominant. To make the theory simple, Maslow ranked these needs in a hierarchical fashion;

Physiological Needs: Physiological needs according to Maslow (1970) are the basic needs for survival and deemed it to be the lowest- level needs. These needs included needs such as food, water and shelter. These are the basic necessities a human being needs to survive and as a matter of fact cannot do without it.

Safety Needs: The next level in the hierarchy was what he termed as safety needs- the search for shelter, security, stability, dependency, protection, freedom from (anxiety, fear and chaos), and a need for structure, order, and law. In the work setting this needs translate into a need for at least a minimal degree of employment security; and the assurance that we cannot be dismissed or sacked on irrelevant issues and that appropriate levels of effort and productivity will ensure continued employment.

Social Needs (belongingness needs): According to Hayes (2009), if a person has the

first two levels of needs well gratified, the emergence of social needs (sense of belongingness and love) becomes the next objective. At this stage in life, a person hunger for the affection of others and would want to be placed in a group or family. Relating this to the work place, as outgoing creatures, humans have a need to belong and this can only be satisfied by an ability to interact with one's colleagues and be able to collaborate effectively to achieve organizational goals.

Esteem Needs: Maslow (1970), observed from the research conducted with his patients that humans after gratifying social needs would now crave for what he calls esteem needs thus, the desire for self-respect, esteem, and the esteem of others. Self-respect he defined as the need for a sense of (achievement, competence, adequacy and confidence). Digesting his submission carefully, and relating it to the workplace setting, externally, people seek needs like desire for reputation and recognition, prestige, status, fame, glory, dominance attention and appreciation in the eyes of other people.

Self-Actualization Needs: The highest need in Maslow's hierarchy, arguable though. Self-actualization refers to the desire for self-fulfilment, realization of a potential, continuous self-development and the process of becoming you.

Conceptual Review

Conducive work environment

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Work environment entails buildings, furniture, and layout as well as the physical condition under which employee operates. This brings us to the definition of environment. Kochan (1990), considers environment in the following context, economic context and social and technological context. It could be looked at as the surrounding of all situation, people, event etc, which influences life. Thus, people who are working in a good environment exert greater effort to perform than those who work in an unhealthy environment. The environment has many effects and opined by the following theorists, graft (1964) commented on the effects of work environment in his write-up. He stated that environmental factors contribute on employees and organizational productivity, equally output, level of wastage and rate of turnover. He further postulated that unhealthy depression and unsafe work environment leads to job dissatisfaction and eventually low productivity. He went further to mention that when an office is grossly deficient in stimulation, the resultant effects are absenteeism, lateness, wastage of resources, disobedience and many other negative attitudes. Hicks (2004) opined that poor working environment exposes employees to injuries, discomfort and helps to reduce productivity. Therefore an organization has to provide a conducive environment that will protect them under emergency condition.

Filippo (2008), postulated that the physical environment as air, the greatest material

resource, without relatively clean air, pure or clean water and hygienic surroundings, people become unfit to work hard for living. He further stated that air should not be polluted and that safety of employees must be protected for higher productivity by ensuring that the physical environment should be devoid of any injury or threat to the life of workers. Hicks (2004), discussed that an organization does not exist in a vacuum. It exist in him, there is nothing a worker can do without the environment being friendly and conducive. As a result of all these, all efforts should be geared towards providing those conditions like enough space, good ventilated offices, adequate light and other materials that will enhance the productivity of employees or organizations. Oliver (2007) in his own contribution stated that that an unsafe physical condition gives rise to accident of which employees are bound to sustain injuries in their work place. Unsafe environment, equipment and tools, polluted air with toxic substance, poor ventilation and inadequate personnel proactive equipment pose a great danger to the health and life of employees. These things drastically help to reduce productivity of organization. He went further to urge employers of labor to provide good working environment that is safe without risk of health and also provides facilities that will ensure the welfare of employees at work.

Chappins (1995), an effective workplace is an environment where results can be achieved as expected by management. An environment

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conducive to the conception and growth of an organization on a sustainable platform of nature's perfection in mankind, and since humans are all created the same, their level of variation is dependent on the environment type (nature vs nurture). Environment creates behavioral patterns in human development either positive or negative depending on the factors we are exposed to. The work environment has physical and psychological effects on any worker or staff of an organization. An accommodating and conducive work environment is a key factor for any organization. This is because results are achieved by the input of humans, a workforce. A comforting environment increases productivity and job satisfaction which has a direct impact on the financial status of organization. For productivity to be at its peak, the energizing environment must be manipulated at all times. Kauno (2005), says productivity is important because it allows the business to be more cost effective. The more output a business has for a specific cause, the cheaper it is to produce the product. This has in turn allows the business to have a higher profit. Productivity on the part of employees is important because getting your job done will help the company's growth. If the company grows and progresses, profit will increase. If profit in the company increases, not only will the management be happier but they will hire more people and give rise to those doing a good job and increase benefits for them. Productivity is good

for everyone and important for a company's survival.

Flexible Work Arrangement

Work Arrangements: A Definition and Examples Workplace Flexibility 2010 defines a "flexible work arrangement" (FWA) as any one of a spectrum of work structures that alters the time and/or place that work gets done on a regular basis.

A flexible work arrangement includes:

1. Flexibility in the scheduling of hours worked, such as alternative work schedules (e.g., flex time and compressed workweeks), and arrangements regarding shift and break schedules
2. Flexibility in the amount of hours worked, such as part time work and job shares;
3. Flexibility in the place of work such as: working at home or at a satellite location.

Our research indicates that workplaces today offer a wide range of flexible work arrangements. What arrangements are provided, and how they are defined, can vary widely. For purposes of discussing policy approaches for advancing FWAs, therefore, we have attempted to impose some coherence on the range of such arrangements by categorizing them along the lines of our definition above – i.e., flexibility in work scheduling; flexibility in number of hours worked; and flexibility in place. The goal of this document is thus primarily to give you a sense of what the "it" is when we talk about FWAs. To achieve that goal, we have provided definitions

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and examples of the most commonly provided FWAs within each category. This document should be used as a glossary reference for our other FWA overview memos. We believe the level of specificity we have provided you in this document is sufficient to discuss policy approaches for increasing and enhancing FWAs in the workplace. Obviously, to implement any particular FWA in a workplace, a much greater level of specificity about the FWA would be required. When reading this document, please remember that the effective implementation of any FWA will necessarily be very work-place-specific, and will offer different levels of control and flexibility to both the employer and the employee.

Flexibility in Work Scheduling, Alternative Work Schedules: Any schedule other than that which is standard to the work setting) Flextime: Schedules based on worker needs within set parameters approved by a supervisor. Examples:• A worker must work 40 hours per week and be present on a daily basis during “core hours” (e.g., from 10:00 am to 3:00 pm), and may, for example,— adjust arrival and departure times as he/she wishes on a daily basis, or— define new standard work hours (e.g., a set schedule of 7:00 am to 3:00 pm every day or of 7:00 am to 3:00 pm on Tues/Thurs and 10:00 am to 6:00 pm on Mon/Wed/Fri).• A worker must work 40 hours per week (but “core hours” do not apply), and may, for example,— vary start and end times on a weekly, or even

daily, schedule;— set a standard schedule as 7:00 am to 3:00 pm on Tues/Thurs (in order to meet the school bus, take a college class, etc.), and 9:00 am to 5:00 pm on Monday/Wednesday/Friday (this form of flextime may be modified to allow the worker to vary a standard schedule as needed—e.g., at exam time, early school dismissal days);— occasionally work extra hours one day to make up for shorter hours worked another day; or— aside from a weekly staff meeting on Friday mornings, work at night to better serve clients in a European time zone. These flextime arrangements may be modified to include situations where the worker is working, but is not present at the worksite (i.e., is teleworking) for all or some portion of the workweek. b) Compressed Workweeks: Workers work full time hours in less than the traditional 5-day workweek by increasing daily hours worked. Examples:• A worker works 10-hour days, 4 days per week (e.g., Monday–Thursday, 8:00 am-6:00 pm).• Over each two-week span, a worker works 9-hour days Monday through Thursday of each week and takes every other Friday off (i.e., works an 8-hour day on the Friday of the first week and does not work the Friday of the second week). These arrangements may be modified to include situations where the worker is working, but not present at the worksite (i.e., is teleworking) for all or some portion of the workweek.

Arrangements Regarding Shifts and Breaks a Shift Arrangement: Workers who

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are assigned shifts by their employers enter into arrangements with their employers giving them more flexibility regarding the shifts they are assigned. Examples: A husband and wife working for the same employer enter into an arrangement to ensure their shifts are staggered so that they will have child care coverage for their 3 children. A worker who cares for an elderly mother during the evenings enters into an arrangement with the employer ensuring that he/she will not have to work the evening or overnight shift.

Break Arrangements: Workers who generally can only take assigned breaks enter into an arrangement with their employers giving them more flexibility over when they take breaks. Example: A worker with diabetes is allowed to set his/her own break schedule in order to ensure an opportunity to eat snacks and meals every three hours.

Flexibility in the Amount of Hours Worked: Part Time Work/Reduced Hours Schedule: Workers who usually work less than 35 hours per week. Examples: A worker works a three-day per week Monday/Wednesday/Friday schedule on a regular basis. A worker works 20 hours per week and determines her own schedule on a weekly basis. A worker goes from working full time to 30 hours per week as she phases into retirement.

Transition Period Part Time: Workers gradually return to work after a major life event (e.g., birth or adoption of a child) by working part

time for a set period and eventually returning to full time work. Examples: Following a six-week maternity leave, a worker returns to work three days a week for six months, four days a week for the next six months, and then to full time work thereafter. A worker's spouse dies unexpectedly and the worker takes off a full month from work. The worker returns to part-time work for two years and then returns to working full time when her children have adjusted to the changed circumstances.

Job Shares: Two or more workers share the duties of one full time job, with each person working on a part time basis. Examples: One worker works Tuesday/Thursday and the other worker work Monday/Wednesday/Friday. Per the employer's direction, they share some tasks of the job and split the others in a way that ensures that the work gets done.

Two workers split the work of a single position 60%/40%, share the salary accordingly, and are in the office 2 days per week at the same time. Two workers share a single position and decide together when each will work and which tasks each will perform. Two workers have unrelated part time assignments but share the same budget line.

Part-year Work: Workers work only a certain number of months per year. Examples: A semi-retired accountant works for an accounting firm during its busy season from January through May. He takes the remainder of the year off to travel. A teacher works a nine-month year. An

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otherwise full-time professional does not work for 8 weeks in the summer.

Flexibility in the Place of Work:

Telework/Home Work: Workers work remotely from their own homes, using a telecommunications connection to the workplace if necessary. Examples: A worker teleworks from home on Monday/Friday, and works at the office Tuesday/Wednesday/Thursday. A garment worker brings materials home from work and sews at her home two days a week (work not involving any telephone or computer connections with the office a policy researcher occasionally works from home when working on a complicated or lengthy document in order to avoid being interrupted. She otherwise works in the office.

Organizational Productivity

Glen (2014) stated that the manufacturing sector is an ever changing beast and every year, the industry is faced with fresh challenges. The author stated that virtually all media houses constantly report the closure of industrial units, labour disputes between employers and their employees or reductions in the labour force due to recession and other economic dynamics. As a result, the image of manufacturing industries have been marred by low wages, high labour turnover, inadequate working conditions, poor performance and productivity (Githinji, 2014). Productivity can be referred to as the quantity of work that is attained in a unit of time by means

of the factors of production. These factors include technology, capital, entrepreneurship, land and labour. It is the link between inputs and outputs and increases when an increase in output occurs with a lesser than comparative increase in input. It also occurs when equal amount of output is generated using fewer inputs (ILO, 2005). Bhatti (2007) and Qureshi (2007) were of the perspective that productivity can be seen as a measure of performance that encompasses both efficiency and effectiveness. It can also be referred to as the ratio of output or production capacity of the workers in an organization. It is the correlation that exists between the quantity of inputs and outputs from a clearly defined process. The performance of a business which determines its continued existence and development is largely dependent on the degree of productivity of its workers. Yesufu (2000) stated that the prosperity of a nation as well as social and economic welfare of its citizens is determined by the level of effectiveness and efficiency of its various sub components. Productivity is a total measure of the efficiency or capacity to transform inputs that is raw materials into finished products or services. More precisely, productivity is a measure that indicates how well essential resources are used to accomplish specified objectives in terms of quantity and quality within a given time frame. It is suitable when measuring the actual output produced compared to the input of resources, taking time into consideration. Hence,

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productivity ratios indicate the extent at which organizational resources are effectively and efficiently used to produce desired outputs. Efficiency takes into account the time and resources required to execute a given task. Therefore, it can be concluded that effectiveness and efficiency are significant predictors of productivity.

Jennifer and George (2006) Argued that the performance of workers contribute directly to an organization's level of effectiveness, efficiency and even towards the achievement of administrative goals. It also stated that a corporation's failure to certify that its workers are motivated has a negative influence on its organizational effectiveness and efficiency thereby affecting employee's productivity levels concerning expected goals and objectives.

Effectiveness

In general, effectiveness is referred to as the degree to which set objectives are accomplished and policies achieve what they were designed to achieve. It focuses on affecting the purpose that is achieving the required or projected results. A program or service is said to be effective if such a program is able to accomplish set objectives or estimated outcomes. As regards workers, it is a measure of how well workers productivity levels meet set goals and objectives of the organization (Yesufu, 2000). Therefore an employee is said to be effective when he/she is able to achieve desired results in line with organizational goals and objectives.

Efficiency

Efficiency on the other hand is productivity of estimated effects; specifically productivity without any form of waste. This has to do with workers abilities to work productively with minimum waste in terms of energy, time and cost. Efficiency is more or less a contrast between the use of inputs in a clearly defined process and generated outputs. For instance, given a specified number of input or resources, a decision making entity be it individual, corporate, administrative institution, or a state realizes a level of output considered to be the maximum achievable based on the present conditions, then such an entity is assumed to be efficient. However if it generates lesser than what it is estimated to generate it is said to be inefficient. As such efficiency stems from the correlation between inputs and outputs, and is referred to basically as the degree to which outputs are produced while minimizing manufacturing costs (Harris, 2001).

Also, previous studies has revealed that at various points in time, low productivity levels have been documented in virtually all establishments be it government or private sectors in Nigeria (Mbogu, 2001; Ezulike, 2001; Iheriohanma, 2006); also conclusions from further studies show that low levels of productivity can be elevated if workers are provided with adequate motivation which may or may not be financial (Tongo, 2005). In terms of productivity, members of a workforce may vary

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in terms of how much value they bring to the organization, which is certainly not limited to the activities they perform but also how well they perform such activities; generally organizational performance is largely dependent on the level of productivity of the workers and various departments that make up the organization. Therefore it is imperative that organizations fairly reward their workforce based on relative productivity and performance levels (Martocchio, 2006). Finally, for workers to perform at higher levels, the organization has a crucial part to play in ensuring that it highly motivates the members of its workforce in order to attract, retain, and improve productivity levels of both workers and the organization as a whole (Reilly, 2003).

Empirical Review

Various studies have examined the effect of extrinsic and intrinsic motivation on a workers' performance and productivity levels. Also most of these studies have obtained different results from their analysis. For instance, Rewards that an individual receives be it intrinsic or extrinsic are very essential in understanding the concept of motivation. Previous studies have proposed that rewards leads to fulfillment and can affect a worker' to be affected, which directly influences the performance as well as productivity levels of the employee. Lawler (1968) stated that certain elements affect worker's productivity levels in relation to their jobs. First, productivity is dependent on the amount of monetary or non-

monetary benefits they actually receive as opposed to the amount they feel they deserve. Also, evaluating what other workers receive in comparison to their own affects their individual performances, while the worker's contentment with both intrinsic and extrinsic rewards acquired has an effect on overall work performance and productivity levels. Furthermore, workers vary largely in the rewards they crave and the degree of value they attribute to each reward. Finally, it is observed that extrinsic rewards tend to please workers more than intrinsic because they lead to the achievement of other rewards. As such, these observations propose the necessity for a diverse reward system. The research carried out by Lin (2007) on the assessment of intrinsic and extrinsic motivation on employee productivity, The results gotten from the examination revealed that there was a significant correlation between extrinsic motivation and the productivity level of the workers, while that of intrinsic motivation was statistically less significant than extrinsic even though a correlation also existed between intrinsic factors and workers' productivity levels. As a result, implications of the findings for future study were stated. Jibowo (2007) in the study; motivation and workplace productivity amongst workers basically assumed the similar methods as (Herzberg, 2000). The study shows some supports for the impact of motivation on productivity. However more value was placed on extrinsic factors than intrinsic. Another research

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by Centres and Bugental (2007), also based their inquiry on Herzberg's twofactor theory of motivation, which divided job variables into several groups: hygiene factors and motivators. They utilized a population of 692 participants to test the rationality of the theory on worker effectiveness and efficiency levels. It was revealed that at higher professional levels, motivators or Intrinsic job elements were more appreciated, while at lower occupational levels hygiene factors or extrinsic job elements were more appreciated. As a result, they concluded that organizations that fulfills both intrinsic and extrinsic elements influencing employees' behavior are able to gain the best out of them.

Also Taylor and Vest (1992) investigated the effect of financial incentives and its removal on workers performance and productivity; it revealed that participants in the experimental group who received personal inducements performed better than those in the control group. Assam (2002) also examined the role of extrinsic and intrinsic motivation on productivity among Nigerian workers, it showed that using a sample of employees of high and low professional levels. The assumption that low income employees will be inherently motivated and highly productive was not validated, and the assumption that higher incomes employees will place great values on intrinsic motivational elements than low income employees was also not validated. This explicitly illustrates the degree of value workers place on extrinsic motivational elements even in

the absence of any significant change in motivational levels across various classes of employees in the organization. (Baase, 2009) perceived that poor compensation is linked to the profitability of an organization. Wage differences amongst high and low salary recipients was linked to the loss of morale, lack of commitment and low productivity. Also Nwachukwu (2004) attributed the decline in productivity levels of employees on some elements, amongst them is a company's failure to cater for the wellbeing of their staff, provide adequate compensation, training and career development, adequate working conditions, suitable working environment and failure to promote cordial relationships amongst co-workers, managers and their organizations which is very demoralizing to the workforce leading to reduced their levels of productivity. Also, in a similar research, (Akerle, 2001) equated the comparative position of ten motivational tools such as pay, training, security, etc. considered external to the job, and other internal factors like employee well-being, good relationships with managers, responsibility etc. among 80 employees of an organization. It was assumed that greater value will be put on internal rather than external job factors. However, findings failed to validate the assumption as it was revealed that two extrinsic factors sufficient compensation and job safety were rated as the most important tools.

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The above are practical works undertaken by various scholars in the area of motivation and productivity. Based on these empirical examinations and conclusions, one may possibly deduce that both intrinsic and extrinsic motivational factors are very essential in improving workers productivity levels in the workplace. As such an individual's performance levels, can be expected to result in higher productivity if the right motivational tools are put in place. However, the question is "to what extent can motivation be it extrinsic or intrinsic induce productivity levels taking into deliberation the arguments for and arguments against the fact that motivation as a concept is complex and relative to individuals.

Gaps in Literature

Despite the increasing effects of motivation on employee productivity, there is still limited literature on its effect in developing countries (Ofori & Aryeetey 2011). This is because while a lot has been documented about the concept of motivation in advanced nations, most works related to motivation in areas concerning productivity in less industrialized nations are hardly found. In addition, it was observed that very little information was provided on intrinsic motivational factors such as relationship with co-workers and managers as it relates to productivity while excess information was provided with regards to extrinsic motivational factors. The existing studies in this relation (Lawler 1968; Lin 2007, Centres & Bugental

2007; Nwachukwu 2004; Baase 2009; Akerele 2001; Jibowo 2007; Taylor & Vest 1992; Assam 2002) amongst others have taken a general focus on performance creating a gap on issues related to productivity. Also, related studies in developing countries have failed to consider the Federal Agencies in South-South, Nigeria. Finally it was observed that very few examinations have been conducted in the aspect of workforce motivation with respect to Federal Agencies in South-South, Nigeria. This study while validating some empirical works has bridged the gap between existing literatures by providing evidence on the effect of workplace motivation on employee productivity in Federal Agencies in South-South, Nigeria.

METHODOLOGY

Descriptive research design and causal research design as well as the survey method was used. The researcher also utilized the survey strategy for this study because it creates room for gathering large amounts of data from a sizeable population in a cost-effective way. The study population was all the twenty (20) federal establishments in South-South Nigeria with over two thousand (2,000) employees. However, due to the large population, we focused the research on the 475 employees from four Federal Agencies in three (3) states in South-South, Nigeria which are: Akwa Ibom State, Rivers State and Bayelsa State. The research instrument would be surveyed on the workforce of the organization considering the fact that they all fall under the

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category of employees within an organization. The sample size was calculated using the “sample size determining for research activity table” by (Krejcie and Morgan, 1970). In estimating the sample size, a 5 percent margin of error (confidence interval) and 95 percent confidence level was used. The sample size for the study therefore is two hundred and seventeen (215) for a sample population of four hundred and seventy five (475). Primary source of data was used for gathering data in this research work. The questionnaire research instrument was used in this research work to gather information because it helps to access a large number of respondents at a minimal cost. After distributing the questionnaires, data would be collected, coded

and analyzed through the use of the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS). Regression analysis and descriptive statistics would be used to validate the data. Furthermore, distribution tables and frequency and percentages would be used for data interpretation.

DATA ANALYSIS

Out of the 217 sets of questionnaire submitted, only 215 were recovered, well filled and thus valid for the data analysis.

Relationship between employees’ promotions and organizational productivity

Table 1: Correlation Result for promotions and organizational productivity

		Promotion	Effectiveness	Efficiency
Promotion	Pearson Correlation	1	.817**	.464**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000
	N	215	215	215
Effectiveness	Pearson Correlation	.817**	1	.569**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000
	N	215	215	215
Efficiency	Pearson Correlation	.464**	.569**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	
	N	215	215	215

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Source: SPSS Output Version 21.0

Table 1 illustrates the test for the first and second postulated bivariate hypothetical statement. The results showed that:

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between Promotion and Effectiveness of federal establishments in South-South Nigeria.

From the result in the table above, the correlation coefficient (rho) shows that there is a significant and positive relationship between Promotion and Effectiveness. The correlation coefficient 0.817 confirms the magnitude and strength of this relationship and it is significant at $p < 0.000 < 0.01$. The correlation coefficient represents a high correlation indicative also of a strong relationship between the variables. Therefore, based on empirical findings the null hypothesis earlier stated is hereby rejected and the alternate upheld. Thus, there is a significant relationship between employees’ promotion and effectiveness in federal establishments in South-South Nigeria.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between Promotion and efficiency of federal establishments in South-South Nigeria.

From the result in the table above, the correlation coefficient (rho) shows that there is a significant and positive relationship between Promotion and efficiency. The correlation coefficient of 0.464 confirms the magnitude and strength of this relationship and it is significant at $p < 0.000 < 0.01$. The correlation coefficient represents a high correlation indicative also of a strong relationship between the variables. Therefore, based on empirical findings the null hypothesis earlier stated is hereby rejected and the alternate upheld. Thus, there is a significant relationship between Promotion and efficiency of federal establishments in South-South Nigeria.

Relationship between employees’ allowances and organizational productivity

Table 3: Correlation Result for employees’ allowances and organizational productivity

		Employees’ Allowances	Effectiveness	Efficiency
Employees’ Allowances	Pearson Correlation	1	.840**	.626**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000
	N	215	215	215
Effectiveness	Pearson Correlation	.840**	1	.621**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000
	N	215	215	215

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	Pearson Correlation	.626**	.621**	1
Efficiency	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	
	N	215	215	215

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Source: SPSS Output Version 21.0

Table 3 illustrates the test for the third and fourth postulated bivariate hypothetical statement. The results show that:

H₀₃: There is no significant relationship between Employee’s allowance and Effectiveness of federal establishments in South-South Nigeria.

From the result in the table above, the correlation coefficient (rho) shows that there is a significant and positive relationship between Employee’s allowance and Effectiveness. The correlation coefficient 0.840 confirms the magnitude and strength of this relationship and it is significant at $p\ 0.000 < 0.01$. The correlation coefficient represents a very high correlation which indicates also a very strong relationship between the variables. Therefore, based on empirical findings the null hypothesis earlier stated is hereby rejected and the alternate upheld. Thus, there is a significant relationship between Employee’s allowance and Effectiveness of federal establishments in South-South Nigeria.

H₀₄: There is no significant relationship between Employee’s allowance and efficiency of federal establishments in South-South Nigeria.

From the result in the table above, the correlation coefficient (rho) shows that there is a significant and positive relationship between Employee’s allowance and efficiency. The correlation coefficient of 0.626 confirms the magnitude and strength of this relationship and it is significant at $p\ 0.000 < 0.01$. The correlation coefficient represents a high correlation indicative also of a strong relationship between the variables. Therefore, based on empirical findings the null hypothesis earlier stated is hereby rejected and the alternate upheld. Thus, there is a significant relationship between Employee’s allowance and efficiency of federal establishments in South-South Nigeria.

Relationship between flexible work arrangement and organizational productivity

Table 5: Correlation Result for flexible work arrangement and organizational productivity

	Flex. Work Arrang.	Effectiveness	Efficiency
Pearson Correlation	1	.838**	.569**

Flexible Work Arrangement	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000
	N	215	215	215
	Pearson Correlation	.838**	1	.533**
Effectiveness	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000
	N	215	215	215
	Pearson Correlation	.569**	.533**	1
Efficiency	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	
	N	215	215	215

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Source: SPSS Output Version 21.0

Table 5 illustrates the test for the fifth and sixth postulated bivariate hypothetical statement. The results showed that:

H₀₅: There is no significant relationship between Flexible Work Arrangement and Effectiveness of federal establishments in South-South Nigeria.

From the result in the table above, the correlation coefficient (rho) shows that there is a significant and positive relationship between Flexible Work Arrangement and Effectiveness. The correlation coefficient 0.838 confirms the magnitude and strength of this relationship and it is significant at $p\ 0.000 < 0.01$. The correlation coefficient represents a very high correlation indicative of a very strong relationship between the variables. Therefore, based on empirical findings the null hypothesis earlier stated is hereby rejected and the alternate upheld. Thus, there is a significant relationship between

Flexible Work Arrangement and Effectiveness in federal establishments in South-South Nigeria.

H₀₆: There is no significant relationship between Flexible Work Arrangement and efficiency of federal establishments in South-South Nigeria.

From the result in the table above, the correlation coefficient (rho) shows that there is a significant and positive relationship between Flexible Work Arrangement and efficiency. The correlation coefficient of 0.569 confirms the magnitude and strength of this relationship and it is significant at $p\ 0.000 < 0.01$. The correlation coefficient represents a moderate correlation between the variables. Therefore, based on empirical findings the null hypothesis earlier stated is hereby rejected and the alternate upheld. Thus, there is a significant relationship between Flexible Work Arrangement and efficiency of federal establishments in South-South Nigeria.

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Relationship between conducive work environment and organizational productivity

Table 6: Correlation Result for conducive work environment and organizational productivity

		Cond. Work Environment	Work Effectiveness	Efficiency
Conducive Environment	Pearson Correlation	1	.562**	.889**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000
	N	215	215	215
Effectiveness	Pearson Correlation	.562**	1	.615**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000
	N	215	215	215
Efficiency	Pearson Correlation	.889**	.615**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	
	N	215	215	215

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Source: SPSS Output Version 21.0

Table 6 illustrates the test for the seventh and eight previously postulated bivariate hypothetical statement. The results showed that:

H₀₇: There is no significant relationship between Conducive work environment and Effectiveness of the federal establishments in South-South, Nigeria.

From the result in the table above, the correlation coefficient (rho) shows that there is a significant and positive relationship between Conducive work environment and Effectiveness. The correlation coefficient 0.562 confirms the magnitude and strength of this relationship and it is significant at $p\ 0.000 < 0.01$. The correlation

coefficient represents a moderate correlation between the variables. Therefore, based on empirical findings the null hypothesis earlier stated is hereby rejected and the alternate upheld. Thus, there is a significant relationship between Conducive work environment and Effectiveness in federal establishments in South-South, Nigeria.

H₀₈: There is no significant relationship between Conducive work environment and efficiency of the federal establishments in South-South, Nigeria.

From the result in the table above, the correlation coefficient (rho) shows that there is a significant and positive relationship between Conducive work environment and efficiency. The correlation coefficient of 0.889 confirms the

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magnitude and strength of this relationship and it is significant at $p\ 0.000 < 0.01$. The correlation coefficient represents a high correlation indicating also a strong relationship between the variables. Therefore, based on empirical findings the null hypothesis earlier stated is hereby rejected and the alternate upheld. Thus, there is a significant relationship between Conducive work environment and efficiency in federal establishments in South-South, Nigeria.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Based on the analyses and findings above, the researcher thus concludes that well motivated employees have the ability to manage stress and can work even when under pressure. Good practices such as work life balance and balanced workload helps in promoting employees' better health and wellness at work, hence employees' assistance policies are key. The specific organizational objectives should be clear, effective supervision, coupled with equality and fairness, recognition, treating employees with dignity and respect. The study concludes that motivational tools through conducive work environment, flexible work arrangement, employee's allowance and promotion significantly influences organizational productivity by way of improved effectiveness and efficiency. Based on the findings and conclusions of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Federal establishments should provide conducive work environment for employees in

order to motivate them in yielding higher organizational productivity.

2. Federal establishments should make effort to know when and where an employee can give out his/her best and flexibility should be applied in scheduling employees to their work place in order to yield optimal productivity.

3. Employees should be motivated through a good pay package as this has a lot to do with their productivity. However, caution need to be taken in order to ensure that there is no abuse of this motivational tools.

4. Employees motivation should not only be financially sided as the placement of employee in a higher position of responsibility resulting from their past effort can influence their productivity better than financial rewards. Employees' promotion a higher pay pack and involvement in the decision making process. Thus, leading to employees' psychological empowerment that significantly influences organizational productivity.

Contribution to Knowledge

This study conclude generally that rewarding of employees effort stimulate them for improved quality performance and encouraged the employee to be more effective and efficient in their dealings. In addition, the study recommends that heads of Federal establishments should allow employees to suggest ways to improve processes as this encourages creativity, innovation and improves quality of work and enhances effectiveness,

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efficiency and overall organization performance and success. Therefore, the main contribution of this study is to add to knowledge that employees' motivational tools proxy of conducive work environment, promotion, flexible work

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